

A Study of Mental Health Among Graduate Student in Relation to Use of Social Media

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Abstract- Human beings are social creatures. We need the companionship of others to thrive in life, and the strength of our connections has a huge impact on our mental health and happiness. Being socially connected to others can ease stress, anxiety, and depression, boost self-worth, provide comfort and joy, prevent loneliness, and even add years to your life. On the flip side, lacking strong social connections can pose a serious risk to your mental and emotional health. In today's world, many of us rely on social media platforms such as Facebook, Twitter, Snapchat, YouTube, and Instagram to find and connect with each other. This paper aimed to study the mental health of students in relation to use of social media. 120 graduate students were taken as sample for the study. Mental health inventory developed by Jagdish & Srivastva and Social media scale (Self made Questionnaire) were used for data collection. Coefficient of correlation and t-test were used by the researcher for analysis of data. The results show that a positive and significant correlation between mental health and use of social media was found among graduate students. No significant difference of mental health among male and female, urban and rural graduate students was found. Male students are using more social media as compare to their female counterparts.

Keywords- Social media, Mental health, Graduate students, Social connections, Psychological well-being, Correlation study, Stress and anxiety.

I. Introduction

A social networking is an online contact service that has managed to create and connect people with the same kind of interest. Social media or social networking sites such as Facebook, Twitter and LinkedIn have attracted many users. They have adopted these sites in their daily life. Some social media sites strive for a diverse audience, but others run the risk of attracting people based on their common language or national based identification. They are making their blog in the World Wide Web. These sites are becoming very popular as they are constantly attracting many people especially teenagers and young generation as their interests are being catered by these websites. Every day, many students are spending countless hours immersed in social media such as Facebook, Instagram, Twitter or YouTube. At first glance this may seem like a waste of time; However, it also helps students develop important knowledge and social skills. In addition, virtual communities enhance people's friendships and love relationships.

The Internet has created a whole new world of social communication or social networking for young people. Over the past ten years, the online world has changed dramatically. Thanks to the invention of social media, young men and women now exchange thoughts, feelings, personal information, pictures and videos at a truly astonishing rate. They are using e-mail, websites, instant messaging and text messaging to keep in touch with friends and make new ones. While most of the interactions are

positive. New technologies have given young generation a new and powerful platform by which they can target peers through social networking.

II. Concept of Mental Health

Mental health plays a very important role in life of an individual. The term ‘‘Mental Health’’ is an inclusive concept. Good health depends on the state of both body and mind. Each exerts a direct influence on the other. A healthy person is not only physically healthy but also mentally healthy. Mental health is a basic factor that contributes to the maintenance of physical health as well as social effectiveness. If a person is well adjusted, he has good physical health such persons as are happy, healthy and hopeful and have harmonious personality. The expression Mental Health consists of two words Mental and health. Mental is generally related with the mind. Health generally means sound condition or well being or freedom from disease. Mental health in brother sense suggests a degree of happiness. It includes personality, temperament, behavior and character. It reflects the true profile of an individual.

Mental health is the outcome of five types of health i.e. physical, emotional, moral, spiritual and social health. Out of the total health, mental health plays an important role as a person with good mental health can adjust very easily with the changes coming in the environment and in order to achieve this objective it is necessary to have an integrated and balanced personality. To attain such a personality, one should have sound mental health. From this view point, any person possessing the following qualities should be considered mentally –

1. Person free from anxiety & conflict
2. Fully adjusted
3. Self-confident
4. Self-controlled
5. Emotionally stable

Mental health was first described as mental hygiene by Clifford Whittingham Beers in 1908, which founded the National Committee for Mental Hygiene in 1909 and actively campaigned for the rights of the mentally ill. The field of mental health has made many advances, particularly since 1908. Our mental health can vary according to our circumstances & can change across our lifetime, in the same way as our physical health does. Possessing mental health, an individual can adjust properly to his environment and make the best efforts for his own family’s and his society’s progress and betterment.

Thus a mentally healthy person is expected to be happy, contented, at ease with himself and with the world at large, more or less fully realizing his potentials under the existing circumstances, a productive and useful member of the society a relatively well adjusted and at the same time showing no disturbing signs and symptoms of the mentally ill like anxiety, depression, suspicion, frustration, conflict, delusion, abnormal movements, maladjusted with self or society at large etc. it is a person’s overall emotional and psychological condition. Mental Health is such a method of leading life in which person’s adjustment with the environment is complete.

Dianne Hales and Robert Hales considers mental health as the capacity to think rationally, and to cope with the transitions, stresses, traumas and losses that occur in all lives, in ways that allow emotional stability and growth. In general, mentally healthy individuals value themselves, perceive reality as it is, accept its limitations and possibilities, respond to its challenges, carry out their responsibilities, establish and maintain close relationships, deal reasonably with others, pursue work that suits their talent and training and feel a sense of fulfillment that makes the efforts of daily living worthwhile.

K.A. Menninger writes in his book *The Human Mind*- Let us define mental health as the adjustment of human beings to the world and to each other with a maximum of effectiveness and happiness..... It is the ability to maintain adjustment with difficult situations.

According to Crow & Crow, Mental Health includes physical well being, adjustment to mental ability, emotional control, social adjustment and sex adjustment.

According to Wolman (1973), Mental Health is a state of relatively good adjustment, feeling of well being and actualization of one's potentialities and capabilities.

According to WHO Expert Committee on Mental Health (1986), Mental Health means, the capacity of an individual to form harmonious relations with others and to participate in, or contribute constructively to change in his social and physical environment. It also implies his ability to achieve a harmonious and balanced satisfaction of his own conflicting instinctive.

Acc. to W.H.O. "Mental Health is a state of well being in which the individual realizes his or her own abilities and can cope with the normal stress of life, can work productively and fruitfully and is able to make a contribution to his or community." Thus it can be said that mental health is the harmonious functioning of the whole personality to the optimum limit.

This clearly meant that mental health is the person's ability to make positive self-evaluation, to perceive the reality, to integrate the personality, autonomy, group oriented attitude and environmental mastery. Definitions of mental health are changing. It is used to be that a person was considered to have good mental health simply if they showed no signs or symptoms of a mental illness. But in recent years, there has been a shift towards a more holistic approach to mental health. Today we recognize that good mental health is not just the absence of mental illness. Nor is it absolute- some people are more mentally healthy than others, whether you are mentally ill or not. These realizations are prompting a new kind of focus on mental health that identifies components of mental wellness and mental fitness and explore ways to encourage them.

III. Concept of Social Media

In the early days, letters were used to convey their point of view to each other. The telegraph was invented in 1792. It could deliver a message quicker than letters. Telegraph was followed by telephone in 1890 and radio in 1891. Telephones and radios enabled people who lived far away to talk to each other. Technology began to change very rapidly in the twentieth century. After the first supercomputers were built in the

1940s, scientists and engineers began looking for ways to create networks between those computers, and this later led to the birth of the Internet. Email was created in the early days of the Internet. Networking technology improved by the 1970s.

Home computers had become commonplace by the 1980s. The first social media site was created in 1997 named Six Degree. In this, users could upload their profiles and could also make other users their friends. The first blogging site became popular in 1999 which created a sensation in social media and is still very popular today. World Social Media Day was celebrated for the first time on 30 June 2010 across the world. Sixdegree, the world's first social media platform, was launched in 1997. It was founded by Andrew Weinrich. At the same time, in the year 2001, it was closed after it had more than one million users.

Social media is made up of two words - social + media. Therefore, social means - one who belongs to the society, the word society is made up of two Sanskrit words sam and aj. Sam means - gathered and together and Aj means - living together. Hence the word society means a group living together.

Meaning of media- Media means 'media' is the plural of English word 'medium' which means 'medium'. "Two or more means of communication are collectively called 'media'". Media is the primary means of communication to reach the vast majority of the general public.

Therefore, the meaning of social media is such a medium for the people of the society so that they can express their thoughts, feelings in front of others. Such a medium is called social media. We can define social media as the relationship that exists between networks of people. It can be defined in several different ways:

Social media are computer-mediated tools that allow people, companies and other organizations to create, share or exchange information, career interests, ideas and pictures/videos in virtual communities and networks. Social media is a set of online communication channels dedicated to community-based input, interaction, content-sharing and collaboration. Website and Application Dedicated. For forums, there are micro blogging, social networking, social bookmarking, social curation, and wikis.

IV. Some Examples of Social Media

1. Facebook:- Facebook was started in 2004. We use Facebook to upload photos and videos, send messages and keep in touch with friends.

2. YouTube:- YouTube is a video sharing social platform that we use to watch videos and upload videos.

3. Instagram:- Instagram was started in 2010. Instagram is also a social media platform like Facebook. We also use it to upload photos and videos, make friends.

4. LinkedIn:- LinkedIn was created in 2003. It is a social media platform specially designed for professionals. Here people come in search of jobs and connect with other professionals.

5. Twitter:- Twitter was started in 2006. Micro Blogging Site Twitter has also become increasingly popular around the world. Through this we can share our content and ideas.

6. Whatsapp:- Through Whatsapp, we can share photos, audios, videos and locations in addition to messages on the smart phones of other WhatsApp users through the Internet.

7. Pinterest:- Pinterest was started in 2010. It is an image sharing social media site. On this, photos and visual users related to different topics are found.

8. Snapchat:- Snapchat was started in 2011, it has more than 330 million active monthly users and it is being liked a lot among teenagers. The age of the most active users of this platform is around 13 years. With the help of generated content and photos on this platform, users get the option of chatting.

V. Justification of The Study

As we all know that in today's present and modern era, social media has become a part of everyone's life. In today's time, social media has emerged as an important means of connecting people from every corner of the world. Social media has become a game changer in today's time. Through the medium of social media, people share their thoughts and information with the people and with this it is being used in every field.

If social media is used properly and limited, then it is very helpful in the development of the person. Through this, a lot of development and change has taken place in the lives of the people. If it is used more than necessary, then it is very harmful for human beings. That is why it is important to know how it can harm us. For example, by using it excessively, the child can become a victim of cyberbullying. Children can get addicted to mobiles. Sometimes social media can also be the cause of death. This wastes time. And the biggest problem is mental health. This is turning out to be a serious time for the kids. Children are confined to themselves in the family. Children are getting away from their families due to social media. He is spending most of the time on social media like WhatsApp, Facebook and social games etc. Along with this, they affect the mental health of the children and today's children are getting valued. Social media is completely affecting us today where it has many benefits but it also has many disadvantages.

Mental health occupies an important place in the education system aimed at the holistic development of the child and human resource development. World Mental Health Day was established in 1992. That's why Mental Health Day is celebrated every year on 10 October. Mental health is a newly emerging area of research in psychology. The progress of mental health of any nation largely depends on the mental health of its citizens. Educational, intellectual, creative, socio-cultural progress is possible only if the physical, mental, social, emotional and spiritual mental health of the individuals of the nation equally, efficiency and effectiveness depend to a large extent on their all round mental health. One of the goals of education is to help a person become happy and in harmony with the environment. Happiness can come in a person's life only when he is satisfied.

The development of a good society is possible only if the health of the people living in it is mentally, socially and physically. They should be free from any kind of worry and tension and should always be active in achieving their objective. As a result, they should get distinction in their academic achievements. It has often been seen that when a

student is in adolescence, due to one reason or the other, many factors affect mental health. For example, environment, social, family factors, heredity and social media also affect adolescence to a great extent. In order to motivate their aspirations, abilities and potential, it becomes absolutely necessary to know this fact that how to provide the right direction to the mental health and development of the students and how to solve this problem. I have chosen this episode because there are many benefits of social media. But along with the many benefits of social media, serious side effects are also emerging from its use.

I want to know the effect of social media, and to identify this problem and how we can solve the problem caused by social media and make people aware of the serious problem caused by social media. So that people can take care of their mental health.

Objectives of The Study

- To study the concept of mental health.
- To study the concept of social media.
- To study the mental health among graduate students in relation to their gender.
- To study the mental health among graduate students in relation to their residential back ground.
- To study the relationship between mental health and social media.
- To study the impact of social media among graduate students.

Hypothesis of The Study

1. There exists no significant difference of mental health among graduate students in relation to their gender.
2. There exists no significant difference of mental health among graduate students in relation to their residential back ground.
3. There exists no significant difference relationship between mental health and social media.
4. There exists no significant difference impact of social media on mental health of graduate students.

Delimitation of The Study

1. Present study was delimitation to 120 graduate students only.
2. Present study was delimitation to graduate students of Yamuna Nagar district of Haryana.

Method Used

Descriptive survey method was used by the investigator.

Population and Sample

All the student study in degree colleges of Yamuna Nagar were selected as the population. From this population 120 student from four degree colleges were selected by random sampling technique.

Tools Used

The following tools were used by the investigator

1. Mental health inventory developed and standardized by JAGDISH & SRIVASTAVA
2. Social media scale (Self made Questionnaire)

Statistics Technique Used

The following techniques were used:

1. Coefficient of correlation (r)
2. t-test

Table 1

Coefficient of Correlation between the mental health of the students and use of social media by the graduate students

Variables	Df	R	level of significance
Mental Health social media	118	0.299	Significant at 0.05 level of significance

The table shows the value of coefficient of correlation which is 0.299 between mental health of students and use of social media by the students. The obtained r value is more than table value, so the null hypothesis is rejected.

Table-2

Significance of difference between the mean scores of Mental Health of Male and Female students

Gender	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	level of significance
Male	60	163.83	11.69	1.210	Not significant
Female	60	154	9.19		

The table shows the means score of males and female in Mental Health Inventory are 163.83 and 154 respectively, and S.D. values are 11.69 and 9.19 respectively. The t-value obtained is 1.210 which is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. There exist a significance difference between the mean scores of male and female which regards to mental health.

Table-3

Significance of difference between the mean scores of males and females students using Social Media

Gender	N	Mean	S.D.	t-ratio	level of significance
Male	60	54.35	6.21	9.48	Significant
Female	60	47.71	7.70		

The table shows the means scores of male and female students in Social Media Inventory are, 54.35 and 47.71 respectively and S.D. value are 6.21 and 7.70 respectively. The t-value obtained is 9.48, which is more than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is rejected. There exists a significance difference between the mean scores of male and female with regards to Social Media.

Table-4
 Significance of difference between the mean scores of Mental Health of urban and rural residential background

Residential background	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	level of significance
Urban	44	157.59	11.85	0.342	Not significant
Rural	76	159.68	11.43		

The table shows the means score urban and rural in mental health inventory are 157.59 and 159.68 respectively and S.D. value are 11.85 and 11.43 respectively. The t- value obtained is 0.342 which is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. There exists a significance difference between the mean scores of urban and rural which regards to mental health inventory. The mental health of rural students is more than their urban student counterparts.

Table-5
 Significance of difference between the mean scores of urban and rural residential background using Social Media

residential background	N	Mean	SD	t-ratio	level of significance
Urban	44	51.20	7.86	0.854	Not significant
Rural	76	50.93	7.72		

Table value 2.62 at 0.01, & 1.98 at 0.05 level of significance

The table show the means score urban and rural in social media inventory are 51.20 and 50.93 respectively and S.D. value are 7.86 and 7.72 respectively. The t- value obtained 0.854 which is less than the table value at 0.05 level of significance. Thus the null hypothesis is accepted. There exist a significance difference between the mean scores of urban and rural which regards to social media.

Main Findings of The Study

- A positive and significant correlation between mental health and use of social media was found among graduate students.
- No significant difference of mental health among male and female graduate students was found.
- A significant difference of use of social media among male and female student was found. Male students are using more social media as compare to their female counterparts.
- No significant difference of mental health among urban and rural graduate students was found.
- No significant difference was found use of social media among urban and rural graduate students was found.

VI. Educational Implication of the Study

In summary, the results of this study indicated that social technologies are becoming a big one. part of a teen's life and can be a contributing factor that can affect development of social ability. Interaction with technology for social purposes has become the

mainstream of communication for many over the years. In particular, teens in college have adopted these forms of communication as a paramount way to stay in touch with family and friends. Social networking websites such as Facebook and MySpace, Instagram are the most popular places for these students to spend their time, and are the primary focus of this study.

A significant difference was found to exist between male and female emotions when communicating; Women rated higher levels of nervousness than men when communicating through social techniques. The results showed that most of these college students spend more time socializing face-to-face than using social technologies. However, the results also showed that when adolescents have access to social technologies, they use it as a means to communicate on a daily basis. Considering the above summary, it was clear that social media played a major role in the behavioral change of the respondents.

Young people mostly use social networking sites to communicate with their friends and families. The fact that social media is their part, especially those born in this era of emerging technology, made most of them feel that they cannot do without it. They relied on it for various positive things like research and contact with old friends and getting information about what was happening in their circle nationally or internationally. The purpose of this report is on the positive and negative effects of social media. Social media addiction is very harmful. In collaboration, this report shows the use of social networking among young people. In addition, it describes the patterns of use of social media among students. However, along with

the negative, the positive influences have affected the lives of the students as well. Social media is very beneficial and dangerous for teenagers. These media are not just for passing time or getting addicted to it. The main theme of social media is to connect with the world. When the addiction starts the productivity of the students is reduced to the minimum extent. Another result also emerged that it is practically not proved that social media addiction affects the lives of students. The influence of social media is a hindrance in the path of success for the students. University students are likely to become accustomed to social use because of their impressive environment.

This research showed that college students were more likely to be influenced by social media. Social media is engaging; Not only does it provide another world for college students to make friends with, but it also provides a good way to release the pressure. To some extent, it affects the lives of college students as a whole, including grades. This research also indicates that an approach is needed to better balance the relationship between social media and academic study. Therefore, college students should think more about the balancing equation of social media and academics that, although social media has negative effects on students such as lack of privacy, distracting students from their academic work, taking most of your productive time, and so on, they also have benefits and can be used in a proper way.

For example, students can create online communities to plan Do a project, have a group discussion about class material, or use social media Update on current academic information.

This study and earlier findings showed some remarkable results. First the independent variable influencing the academic performance of the students, i.e. social media participation was negatively related to student outcomes, whereas other The independent variables were positively related to student outcomes. its consequences Study suggests lecturers should create a blueprint for how their students can Maximize the benefits of social media, that college management should incorporate rules and regulations on the use of social media in the college and the government should take adequate control measures to regulate their use among students and lecturers.

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